

ESTIMATION OF AIR POLLUTANTS EMITTED FROM MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES THROUGH MODELLING APPROACH: A CASE STUDY OF AHMEDABAD CITY

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Abstract

The generation of municipal solid waste is an issue that becoming more prominent in the environmental arena. Majority of waste management strategies generate air pollutants which leads to climate change and worsening of air quality it also has a potential for impact on health; therefore, it is crucial to identify effective procedure for measurements of air pollutants and reduction of waste from sources to disposal sites. This study aims to estimate air emissions from Existing waste management practices and develop a suitable waste management scenario for Ahmedabad city. The Present study estimated the air emissions from different waste management strategies through Solid Waste Emission Estimation Tool which has ability to estimate the air pollutants emitted from the different waste management sectors for existing condition and also provide mitigation measures for the reduction of emissions. In Ahmedabad City, 14, 61,460MT municipal solid waste is collected per year which is disposed at landfill or dumpsite. Out of this 4,38,000MT waste is sent for composting ,6,57,000MT for Recycling and 3,65,000MT per year Landfilling which generates overall emission 8,97,693 MTCO_{2e} in year 2021. The present study focused on estimation of air pollutants through SWEET and also provided different alternate scenarios for the reduction of air pollutants generated from MSW sectors. Out of all scenarios, Scenario-4 Increase Composting& Recycling along with Fuel Change was the best. This scenario, handle the 14,61,460 MT/Year MSW via 5,84,000MT/Year Composting, 7,30,000MT/Year Recycling and 1,46,000MT/Year Landfilling which reduces the overall emission up to 6,13,198 MTCO_{2e} in year 2030, which includes 94,405 MTCO_{2e}/Year from Collection& Transportation; 47,130 MTCO_{2e}/Year from Organics Management; 89,062MT CO_{2e}/Year from Waste Handling Equipment and 4,71,663 MT CO_{2 e}/Year from Landfilling& LFG Combustion sector. Route Optimization was also carried out as an alternate scenario for reduction of air emission from Collection-Transportation of MSW. It was done for Ghatlodia ward North West Zone. By optimizing route, reduce the emission from Collection-Transportation sector up to 2311.1680 MT CO_{2e} and 2542.080 MT CO_{2e} by route optimization along with Fuel change.

Keywords: Municipal Solid Waste, Waste Management Strategies, Scenarios, Air Emission, SWEET.

INTRODUCTION

Municipalities experiencing rapid urbanization are facing increased pressure on their socio-economic and environmental prospects due to migration and the depletion of natural resources. As per the central pollution control board (CPCB) of India, the per capita waste generation has increased at an exponential rate (0.26 kg/day to 0.85 kg/day). It is estimated that approximately 80% to 90% of the municipal waste is

disposed-off in landfills without proper management practices. The society and citizens are not much aware about the management of waste and their related issues, their careless attitude towards their waste create challenges for the municipalities. The potential threat about MSW at dumpsite and landfill site which emits harmful air pollutants and leading to the environmental pollution. In India approximately 1, 43,449 MT of MSW is being generated daily, out of which around 1, 11,000 MT collected and about 35,602 MT are treated. There are provisions for estimation of air pollutants from different MSW sectors. This estimation is done by manual method that is very complex, not feasible and required skilled manpower as well as sophisticated instruments. Instead of this conventional method, the present study adopts the modelling approach or any tool for estimation which will be economical, feasible, and easily applicable and also suggests mitigation measures for reduction of air pollutants. The present study uses SWEET Tool (Solid waste emission and estimation tool) software for estimation of different air pollutants concentration such as CO₂, NO_x, Black Carbon, PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ from collection to disposal facilities of MSW. The advantage of this tool that it gives summary sheets of emissions in the graphical form, it predicts the present, past, future emissions with 4 different alternate scenarios.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The air emissions monitoring requires sophisticated instruments as well as skilled manpower combine with the conventional method. Though the conventional methods are complicated, time consuming and also not cost effective. Whereas modelling tool is much more flexible than the conventional monitoring as it produces results in hours at lower cost. It also provides the mitigation measures to minimize the air emissions and its impact. There are number of Tools such as IPCC, LandGEM, WARM, IWM, SWM GHG Calculator, EQT, SWEET tool used for the estimation of air pollutants emitted from MSW. The table no 1 shows the comparison of SWEET tool and EQT.

Table 1: Comparison of SWEET TOOL and EQT

Parameters	SWEET	EQT
Pollutants	CO ₂ , BC, OC, CH ₄ , NO _x , PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , SO _x	CO ₂ , CH ₄ , CO ₂ , N ₂ O
Activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collection & Transportation Waste Handling Equipment Waste Burning Organics Management Landfills & LFG Combustion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collection & Transportation Composting Anaerobic Digestion Incineration Recycling MBT Waste Burning Landfilling & LFG Combustion Uncollected Waste
Key Input	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste Collection Rate Projected Future and Historical included Waste collection data in MTA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not Included Waste Collection data in MTD For Existing & alternate scenarios it gives options in two steps:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For Existing & alternate scenarios it gives 4 options: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Composting 2. Recycling 3. Anaerobic Digestion 4. Combustion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Step:1 Treatment of Segregated waste <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Composting 2. Recycling 3. Anaerobic Digestion ➤ Step:2 Treatment of Mixed waste <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Incineration 2. MBT 3. Landfilling
Output	It gives output in the different sheet including Overall Summary Emission, Summary Changes vs BAU, BAU Emits, Alt emit-1 to 4, Open burning Emit and Graphical Form	Output of this tool includes summary of both with respect to individual treatment methods and various analysed scenarios in the form of table as well as graphical form.
Prediction of Emissions	Present, Past and Future with 4 different alternate scenarios	Present year with 4 different alternate scenarios
Emission	Gross Emission	Net Emission
Unit	MT and MT CO ₂ e	Kg/Tonne and Kg of CO ₂ e/Tonne

Based on above criteria “Solid Waste Emission Estimation Tool (SWEET)” was selected for the estimation of air pollutants emitted from municipal solid waste management strategies. To effectively use the Solid Waste Emissions Estimation Tool (SWEET) for Ahmedabad’s municipal solid waste management, it’s important to collect specific secondary data about the city's waste management system.

Materials:

The secondary data regarding existing municipal solids waste management system of Ahmedabad city were required to run SWEET tool.

Table 2: Secondary data of MSWM

Population in formal collection zones	70,00,000 Approx.
Population outside formal collection zones	0
Average annual precipitation (mm/year)	782
Mean annual temperature (°C)	30
Per capita waste generation rate <u>inside</u> formal collection zones (kg/capita/day) or Total waste generated annually inside formal collection zones in metric tons.	0.572

Per capita waste generation rate <u>outside</u> formal collection zones (kg/capita/day) or Total waste generated annually outside formal collection zones in metric tons.	0.0
Total waste <u>collected</u> annually inside formal collection zones (metric tons)	14,61,460
Average annual growth in quantity of waste collected – historical	1.33% *
Average annual growth in quantity of waste collected - projected future	5.0% *
Percentage of waste generated <u>inside</u> formal collection zones that is collected	100
Percentage of waste generated <u>outside</u> formal collection zones that is collected	0.0
Average waste composition	In percentage**
Food waste	43.50
Green waste	0.0
Wood waste	9.90
Paper / cupboard waste	12.90
Textiles waste	2.70
Plastic waste	7.20
Metal waste	3.30
Glass waste	4.0
Tire waste	0.90
Other waste	16.30
Total	100.0
<u>Existing scenario:</u>	
Composting	
Composting facility opening year or planned opening year (diversion scenario starts year)	1997
Metric Tons of Waste Delivered to Composting Facility Per Year	4,38,000
Composition of Waste From Food waste	100%
Recycling	
Recycling facility opening year or planned opening year (diversion scenario starts year)	2002
Metric Tons of Waste Delivered to Recycling Facility Per Year	6,57,000

For Collection & Transportation of waste:

For collection and transportation	
Number of heavy-duty diesel trucks in operation each year	950
Number of heavy-duty gasoline trucks in operation each year	550
Number of heavy-duty natural gas trucks in operation each year	-
Number of light-duty diesel trucks in operation each year	-
Number of light-duty gasoline trucks in operation each year	-
Number of light-duty natural gas trucks in operation each year	-
Kilometres travelled by typical light-duty truck per year	38,624
Kilometres travelled by typical heavy-duty truck per year	37,659

1.	No. of Households	28,560
2.	Total Number of Person involve in Collection	32
3.	Frequency of Waste collection	Daily
4.	Number of Vehicles used for collection	16
5.	Type of vehicle used for collection	Chhota Hathi
6.	Amount of Waste daily collected and sent to TS	65MT
7.	Number of Trips per day	48
8.	Cost of waste collection from Household to Transfer station (Fuel + labor cost + No. of trips+ distance)	1500 Rs per MT
9.	Provide POI of Waste collection route	
9.	Amount of Waste daily collected and sent to TS	60MT
10.	Number of Trips per day	39
11.	Cost of waste collection from Household to Transfer station (Fuel + labor cost + No. of trips+ distance)	1500 Rs per MT
12.	Provide POI of Waste collection route	

In Ghatlodia ward there are 11 routes, the below table no 3 shows only one route detail. The Routes details are required for the air pollutants emissions due to transportation.

Table 3: Only 1 route detail of Ghatlodiya ward

Route	POI Name	Collection Time	Latitude	Longitude	Assigned Vehicle
Route-01	Ramkrishna nagar	6:13AM	23°04'29.18"	72°32'46.56"	GJ-01-FT-0425
Route-01	Ankit Socceity	6:09AM	23°04'25.13"	72°32'50.26"	GJ-01-FT-0425
Route-01	Jineshwar Flats	7:20AM	23°04'17.28"	72°32'42.15"	GJ-01-FT-0425
Route-01	Saundarya Nihar	2:46PM	23°04'17.59"	72°32'44.49"	GJ-01-FT-0425
Route-01	kantipark Socceity	7:23AM	23°04'17.02"	72°32'40.48"	GJ-01-FT-0425
Route-01	Chaya flat	1:34PM	23°04'16.16"	72°32'37.20"	GJ-01-FT-0425
Route-01	Aarjanbhai Ni chali	6:18AM	23°04'23.05"	72°32'27.34"	GJ-01-FT-0425
Route-01	Shankarnagar	6:17AM	23°03'49.86"	72°33'41.71"	GJ-01-FT-0425
Route-01	Arbudadevi Socceity Vibhag 2	6:14AM	23°04'26.18"	72°32'37.63"	GJ-01-FT-0425

Route-01	Nandanvan Apprtment	6:03AM	23°04'06.93"	72°34'14.42"	GJ-01-FT-0425
Route-01	Hajaribag Soceity	6:59AM	23°04'13.25"	72°32'36.07"	GJ-01-FT-0425
Route-01	Samarapan Apprtment	7:12AM	23°04'14.59"	72°32'42.95"	GJ-01-FT-0425
Route-01	Panchedhar Mandir	7:14AM	23°04'10.82"	72°32'41.85"	GJ-01-FT-0425

METHODOLOGY

[A] Existing Scenario:

Collection, transportation, Treatment and disposal of municipal, industrial and other SW produces measurable quantities of air pollutants. The estimation of emissions was done using SWEET software.

Ahmedabad city generates 4000 Metric Tons of municipal solid waste on a daily basis. This waste is collected; transported, treated and remaining waste is disposed at Dump site. Door to Door collection and spot to dump collection system is used for the collection of waste. 100% waste is collected by the AMC.

The following figure shows the existing scenario of solid waste management of Ahmedabad city.

The present study focused on the overall emissions of pollutants from existing and alternative scenarios generated and suggested based on the SWEET software. Total 1500 Diesel based heavy and light duty vehicles are used in the collection of Municipal

solid waste from the city. Solid Waste Emission Estimation Tool estimate overall emission from the collection-transportation as well as various pollutants like Black carbon, CO₂, NO_x, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} emitted from this sector.

Table 4: Emissions CO₂, NO_x, Black Carbon, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} from Collection-Transportation through Existing Scenario in MT

Year	CO ₂	NO _x	Black Carbon	PM ₁₀	PM _{2.5}
2015	42,678	212	36	15	13
2016	43,246	215	37	15	14
2017	43,821	218	37	15	14
2018	44,404	220	38	15	14
2019	44,994	223	38	15	14
2020	45,593	226	39	16	14
2021	46,199	229	39	16	15
2022	48,509	241	41	17	15
2023	50,934	253	43	17	16
2024	53,481	266	45	18	17
2025	56,155	279	48	19	18
2026	58,963	293	50	20	19
2027	61,911	307	52	21	19
2028	65,007	323	55	22	20
2029	68,257	339	58	23	21
2030	71,670	356	61	24	23

The organic management sector includes handling of organics waste and major pollutant generating from this sector was Methane (CH₄).

Table 5: Methane Emission from Organics Management through Existing Scenario

Year	Emission, MTCO ₂ e	Emission, MT
2015	35,716	1,429
2016	36,192	1,448
2017	36,673	1,467
2018	37,161	1,486
2019	37,655	1,506
2020	38,156	1,526
2021	38,663	1,547
2022	40,596	1,624
2023	42,626	1,705
2024	44,757	1,790
2025	46,995	1,880
2026	49,345	1,974
2027	51,812	2,072
2028	54,403	2,176
2029	57,123	2,285
2030	59,979	2,399

Landfill site is the main source of methane emission which is one of the major contributors in greenhouse gases. Annually 1, 46,000MT waste is goes for Landfilling.

Table 6: Methane Emissions from landfilling & LFG Combustion Existing Scenario

Year	Emission, MTCO ₂ e	Emission, MT
2015	6,33,411	25,336
2016	6,44,791	25,792
2017	6,57,649	26,306
2018	6,70,738	26,830
2019	6,84,028	27,361
2020	6,97,497	27,900
2021	7,11,127	28,445
2022	7,24,905	28,996
2023	7,41,192	29,648
2024	6,88,565	27,543
2025	6,42,581	25,703
2026	6,02,210	24,088
2027	5,66,588	22,664
2028	5,34,993	21,400
2029	5,06,820	20,273
2030	4,81,560	19,262

[B] Alternate Scenario:

As per the results of Existing scenario of municipal solid waste handling, collection-transportation and landfilling were the major source of air emission from the waste sector. For the reduction of air emission various alternative scenarios were developed by SWEET tool.

Scenario-1 (Increase Composting)

As per BAU (Existing Scenario) percentage of composting, recycling and for Landfilling was 30%, 45% and 25% respectively. In this scenario, percentage of Composting was increasing 10%.

Waste Collection rate for future projected 5% there was no change in fuel consumption and number of vehicles used for the collection of waste. Waste handling equipment remains same.

There was only change in percentage of waste collection rate and percentage of composting. This scenario will start from 2022. The following table shows the sector wise emissions through scenario-1

Table 7: Sector Wise total Emissions from Scenario-1 in MTCO_{2e}

Year	Collection & Transportation	Landfilling & LFG Combustion	Organics Management	Waste Handling Equipment	Total
2015	67,787	6,33,411	35,716	68,843	8,05,758
2016	68,688	6,44,791	36,192	69,759	8,19,430
2017	69,602	6,57,649	36,673	70,687	8,34,611
2018	70,528	6,70,738	37,161	71,627	8,50,053
2019	71,466	6,84,028	37,655	72,580	8,65,728
2020	72,416	6,97,497	38,156	73,545	8,81,614
2021	73,379	7,11,127	38,663	74,523	8,97,693
2022	0	7,24,905	53,371	0	7,78,275
2023	0	7,08,722	54,438	0	7,63,160
2024	0	6,61,254	55,527	0	7,16,781
2025	0	6,19,588	56,637	0	6,76,225
2026	0	5,82,832	57,770	0	6,40,602
2027	0	5,50,239	58,925	0	6,09,165
2028	0	5,21,183	60,104	0	5,81,287
2029	0	4,95,137	61,306	0	5,56,444
2030	0	4,71,663	62,532	0	5,34,195

Scenario-1 affects the Organics waste management and Landfilling & Combustion Sectors as in this scenario amount of organics waste handling increases, emissions from Organics Management increases with respect to time and decreases from Landfilling& LFG Combustion. Major Pollutant from these two sectors was methane and its emission shown in below table no 8 in MTCO_{2e} and MT. There was no change found in Collection-Transportation and Waste Handling Equipment Sectors.

Table 8: Methane Emissions from Landfilling& LFG Combustion and Organics Management through Scenario-1

Year	Landfilling & LFG Combustion, MTCO ₂ e	Organics Management, MTCO ₂ e	Landfilling& LFG Combustion, MT	Organics Management, MT
2015	6,33,411	35,716	25,336	1,429
2016	6,44,791	36,192	25,792	1,448
2017	6,57,649	36,673	26,306	1,467
2018	6,70,738	37,161	26,830	1,486
2019	6,84,028	37,655	27,361	1,506
2020	6,97,497	38,156	27,900	1,526
2021	7,11,127	38,663	28,445	1,547
2022	7,24,905	53,371	28,996	2,135
2023	7,08,722	54,438	28,349	2,178
2024	6,61,254	55,527	26,450	2,221
2025	6,19,588	56,637	24,784	2,265
2026	5,82,832	57,770	23,313	2,311
2027	5,50,239	58,925	22,010	2,357
2028	5,21,183	60,104	20,847	2,404
2029	4,95,137	61,306	19,805	2,452
2030	4,71,663	62,532	18,867	2,501

Scenario-2 (Increase Recycling):

BAU (Existing Scenario) handle 30% waste by composting, 45% waste by recycling and 25% via landfilling. In this second scenario percentage of waste treated via recycling was

15% change from BAU. There was only change in percentage of waste collection rate that was 5% and percentage of recycling was 60% and it was assumed that this scenario will be applicable from 2022. The following table shows the sector wise emissions through scenario-2

Table 9: Sector wise overall emission from scenario-2

Year	Collection & Transportation	Landfilling & LFG Combustion	Organics Management	Waste Handling Equipment	Total
2015	67,787	6,33,411	35,716	68,843	8,05,758
2016	68,688	6,44,791	36,192	69,759	8,19,430
2017	69,602	6,57,649	36,673	70,687	8,34,611
2018	70,528	6,70,738	37,161	71,627	8,50,053
2019	71,466	6,84,028	37,655	72,580	8,65,728
2020	72,416	6,97,497	38,156	73,545	8,81,614
2021	73,379	7,11,127	38,663	74,523	8,97,693
2022	0	7,24,905	39,436	0	7,64,341
2023	0	7,08,722	40,225	0	7,48,947
2024	0	6,61,254	41,030	0	7,02,283
2025	0	6,19,588	41,850	0	6,61,438
2026	0	5,82,832	42,687	0	6,25,520
2027	0	5,50,239	43,541	0	5,93,780
2028	0	5,21,183	44,412	0	5,65,594
2029	0	4,95,137	45,300	0	5,40,438
2030	0	4,71,663	46,206	0	5,17,869

This Scenario decreases the emission from Organics waste management and Landfilling & LFG Combustion by increasing the recycling of waste and reducing the percentage of waste treated via composting and landfilling.

This Scenario mainly affect the Organics waste management and Landfilling & Combustion Sectors as in this scenario amount of organics waste handling and Landfilling was decreases.

Major Pollutant from these two sectors was methane and its emission show below table no 10 in MTCO_{2e} and MT. There was no change found in Collection-Transportation and Waste Handling Equipment Sectors.

Table 10: Methane Emissions from Scenario-2

Year	Landfilling& LFG Combustion, MTCO _{2e}	Organics Management, MTCO _{2e}	Landfilling& LFG Combustion, MT	Organics Management, MT
2015	6,33,411	35,716	25,336	1,429
2016	6,44,791	36,192	25,792	1,448
2017	6,57,649	36,673	26,306	1,467
2018	6,70,738	37,161	26,830	1,486
2019	6,84,028	37,655	27,361	1,506
2020	6,97,497	38,156	27,900	1,526
2021	7,11,127	38,663	28,445	1,547
2022	7,24,905	39,436	28,996	1,577
2023	7,08,722	40,225	28,349	1,609
2024	6,61,254	41,030	26,450	1,641
2025	6,19,588	41,850	24,784	1,674
2026	5,82,832	42,687	23,313	1,707
2027	5,50,239	43,541	22,010	1,742
2028	5,21,183	44,412	20,847	1,776
2029	4,95,137	45,300	19,805	1,812
2030	4,71,663	46,206	18,867	1,848

Scenario-3 (Fuel Change):

In Scenario-3, the fuel used for waste collection and transportation was changed, with diesel-based vehicles replacing the previously used fuel. The table below outlines the sector-wise emissions for Scenario-2 for comparison.

Table 11: Sector wise overall Emission from Scenario-3

Year	Collection & Transportation	Landfilling & LFG Combustion	Organics Management	Waste Handling Equipment	Total
2015	67,787	6,33,411	35,716	68,843	8,05,758
2016	68,688	6,44,791	36,192	69,759	8,19,430
2017	69,602	6,57,649	36,673	70,687	8,34,611
2018	70,528	6,70,738	37,161	71,627	8,50,053
2019	71,466	6,84,028	37,655	72,580	8,65,728
2020	72,416	6,97,497	38,156	73,545	8,81,614
2021	73,379	7,11,127	38,663	74,523	8,97,693
2022	80,512	7,24,905	39,436	0	8,44,853
2023	82,122	7,08,722	40,225	0	8,31,069
2024	83,764	6,61,254	41,030	0	7,86,048
2025	85,440	6,19,588	41,850	0	7,46,878
2026	87,148	5,82,832	42,687	0	7,12,668
2027	88,891	5,50,239	43,541	0	6,82,672
2028	90,669	5,21,183	44,412	0	6,56,264
2029	92,482	4,95,137	45,300	0	6,32,920
2030	94,332	4,71,663	46,206	0	6,12,201

In this scenario, the Waste Handling Equipment sector remains unaffected as there is no change in the fuel used in this sector. Emissions from Landfilling and Landfill Gas (LFG) Combustion decrease over time, likely due to improved waste management practices and better methane capture technologies. In contrast, emissions from Organics Management increase over time, possibly due to a rise in the volume of organic waste or the use of more energy-intensive processing methods. The pollutants emitted from Collection and Transportation, Landfilling and LFG Combustion, and Organics Management are detailed, showing how emission trends vary across these stages.

Emission from Collection-Transportation Sector:

Major Pollutants emitted from Waste Collection-Transportation Sectors were CO₂, NO_x, Black Carbon and CH₄. Following table 12 shows the emission of this pollutants in MTCO_{2e} and in MT. As shown at table 12, we can see that emission from collection-transportation increases with time. In this scenario we replace diesel-based vehicle with

natural gas and its emission factors for CO₂, NO_x and CH₄ are higher compared to diesel vehicle. This scenario decreases the emission of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and Black Carbon with respect to time as emission factors are lower compared to Diesel based vehicle.

Table 12: emission of air pollutants from Collection-Transportation Sector

Year	CO ₂	NO _x	Black Carbon	CH ₄	PM ₁₀	PM _{2.5}
2015	42,678	212	36	0	15	13
2016	43,246	215	37	0	15	14
2017	43,821	218	37	0	15	14
2018	44,404	220	38	0	15	14
2019	44,994	223	38	0	15	14
2020	45,593	226	39	0	16	14
2021	46,199	229	39	0	16	15
2022	68,335	226	21	26	9	8
2023	69,701	230	22	27	9	8
2024	71,095	235	22	27	9	8
2025	72,517	240	22	28	9	8
2026	73,967	245	23	28	10	9
2027	75,447	249	23	29	10	9
2028	76,956	254	24	29	10	9
2029	78,495	259	24	30	10	9
2030	80,065	265	25	31	10	9

Year	CO ₂	NO _x	Black Carbon	CH ₄
2015	42,678	-6,569	32,504	5
2016	43,246	-6,656	32,936	5
2017	43,821	-6,745	33,374	5
2018	44,404	-6,834	33,818	5
2019	44,994	-6,925	34,268	5
2020	45,593	-7,017	34,724	5
2021	46,199	-7,111	35,186	5
2022	68,335	-7,003	19,014	654
2023	69,701	-7,143	19,394	667
2024	71,095	-7,286	19,782	680
2025	72,517	-7,431	20,178	694
2026	73,967	-7,580	20,581	708
2027	75,447	-7,732	20,993	722
2028	76,956	-7,886	21,413	736
2029	78,495	-8,044	21,841	751
2030	80,065	-8,205	22,278	766

Emission from Landfilling &LFG Combustion and Organics Management Sector:

Major pollutant from Landfilling & LFG Combustion and Organics Management is Methane. Following table 6.11 represent the emission from these two sectors through scenario-3.

Table No 13: Methane emissions from Different sector of MSWM

Year	Landfilling& LFG Combustion, MTCO ₂ e	Organics Management, MTCO ₂ e	Landfilling& LFG Combustion, MT	Organics Management, MT
2015	6,33,411	35,716	25,336	1,429
2016	6,44,791	36,192	25,792	1,448
2017	6,57,649	36,673	26,306	1,467
2018	6,70,738	37,161	26,830	1,486
2019	6,84,028	37,655	27,361	1,506
2020	6,97,497	38,156	27,900	1,526
2021	7,11,127	38,663	28,445	1,547
2022	7,24,905	39,436	28,996	1,577
2023	7,08,722	40,225	28,349	1,609
2024	6,61,254	41,030	26,450	1,641
2025	6,19,588	41,850	24,784	1,674
2026	5,82,832	42,687	23,313	1,707
2027	5,50,239	43,541	22,010	1,742
2028	5,21,183	44,412	20,847	1,776
2029	4,95,137	45,300	19,805	1,812
2030	4,71,663	46,206	18,867	1,848

Scenario-4 (Increase Recycling& Composting with fuel change)

In the existing scenario, waste is managed through a combination of methods: 30% is composted, 45% is recycled, and the remaining 25% is sent to landfills. In this analysis, an integrated approach was taken by simultaneously modifying the proportions of composting and recycling, alongside changes in fuel type used in waste management processes. The objective was to evaluate the cumulative impact of these changes on overall emissions.

Scenario-4 Increase Composting& Recycling with Fuel Change	Heavy Duty Vehicle	Diesel	500	Recycling 50% (7,30,000MTY)	Composting 40% (5,84,000MTY)	Landfilling 10% (1,46,000)
		CNG	450			
	Light Duty Vehicle	Diesel	300			
		CNG	250			

Year	Emission
2015	8,05,758
2016	8,19,430
2017	8,34,611
2018	8,50,053
2019	8,65,728
2020	8,81,614
2021	8,97,693
2022	8,45,703
2023	8,31,936
2024	7,86,933
2025	7,47,780
2026	7,13,589
2027	6,83,611
2028	6,57,221
2029	6,33,897
2030	6,13,198

Comparison of Emissions Across All Scenarios:

Below graph provide a comparative overview of total emissions across all modeled scenarios. Specifically, Table no 14 presents a detailed comparison of air pollutant emissions from various waste management sectors for the year 2030.

This includes sector-wise emissions such as those from Collection and Transportation, Landfilling and LFG Combustion, and Organics Management, enabling a clear evaluation of each scenario's environmental impact.

Table 14: Comparison of air emission from all scenarios

Parameter		BAU	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4
Overall Emission, MTCO ₂ e per Year		7,70,985	5,34,195	5,17,869	6,12,201	6,13,198
Sector wise Total Emission in MTCO ₂ e per Year and Pollutant wise in MT						
Collection-Transportation	Pollutant in MTY	87,695 MTCO ₂ e per Year	87,695 MTCO ₂ e per Year	87,695 MTCO ₂ e per Year	94,332 MTCO ₂ e per Year	94,405 MTCO ₂ e per Year
	CO ₂	71,670	71,670	71,670	80,199	80,137
	NO _x	356	356	356	229	265
	Black Carbon	61	61	61	39	25
	PM ₁₀	24	24	24	16	10
	PM _{2.5}	23	23	23	15	9
Landfilling & LFG Combustion	Pollutant in MTY	4,80,604 MTCO ₂ e per Year	4,71,663 MTCO ₂ e per Year	4,60,663 MTCO ₂ e per Year	4,71,663 MTCO ₂ e per Year	4,60,663 MTCO ₂ e per Year
	CH ₄	19,262	18,667	17,607	18,867	17,607
Organics Management	Pollutant in MTY	46,206 MTCO ₂ e per Year	62,532 MTCO ₂ e per Year	46,206 MTCO ₂ e per Year	46,206 MTCO ₂ e per Year	47,130 MTCO ₂ e per Year
	CH ₄	2399	2501	1848	2399	1885
Waste Handling Equipment	Pollutant in MTY	89,062 MTCO ₂ e per Year				
	CO ₂	47,658	47,658	47,658	47,658	47,658
	NO _x	281	281	281	281	281
	Black Carbon	57	57	57	57	57
	PM ₁₀	101	101	101	101	101
	PM _{2.5}	97	97	97	97	97

[C] Route Optimization with respect to air quality

Waste Collection-Transportation is the major contributor in air emission. According to one data Transportation sector generates approximately 29% of the total greenhouse gas emissions and 25% of the global energy related carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions.[11] Results of air emission from this sector estimated through SWEET also shows the air emission from the waste collection- transportation was highest and if this scenario remains continues in future, then it will emit more air pollutants. To reduce the air emission from waste collection-transportation sector, route optimization is one of the important strategies. By optimizing route, we can reduce the distance travelled by collection vehicle and emission vice versa. In this study the route will be optimized through **Optimo-Route** and emission from the optimized and existing routes were described. Below figure shows the existing and optimized route of Ghatlodiya ward of Ahmedabad city along with air emissions.

Existing route Ghatlodiya Ward

Optimized route of Ghatlodiya Ward

Table No 15: Comparison of distance travelled by vehicle through Existing and Optimized Route

Route	Distance Travelled (Km)		
	Existing	Optimized	Reduction
1.	15.7	15	0.7
2.	11.6	11	0.6
3.	8.51	8	0.51
4.	14.4	13	1.4
5.	12	11	1
6.	11.8	11	0.8
7.	18.6	16	2.6
8.	15.2	12	3.2
9.	12.4	10	2.4
10.	15.2	14	1.2
11.	7.86	7	0.86
Total	144.27	128	16.27

[D] Estimation of Air Emission from Existing Route and Optimized Route of Waste Collection-Ghatlodia Ward

1. Existing Route:

Emission of air pollutants emitted from collection-transportation was calculated using following equation:
$Emission = EF_{Trans.} * D * Mass$ [5]
Where, $EF_{Trans.}$ = Fuel emission factor, kg of Gas/kg/km
D = Distance, km
Mass = Mass of Solid Waste, kg
Total Distance of Route-1 to 11 = 144.27 Km
Total mass of solid waste = 60MT = 60,000kg
Fuel used in Vehicle - Diesel
Type of Vehicle – Light duty vehicle
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emission of CO₂ from Existing Route = $0.301 * 144.27 * 60,000 = 2,605,516.2$ Kg CO₂ Emission of NO_x from Existing Route = $0.001191 * 144.27 * 60,000 = 10,309.5342$ Kg NO_x Emission of Black Carbon from Existing Route = $0.000241 * 144.27 * 60,000 = 2086.1442$ Kg Black Carbon Emission of PM_{2.5} from Existing Route = $0.000146 * 144.27 * 60,000 = 1263.8052$ kg PM_{2.5}

2. Optimized Route:

Here, two type of scenarios were developed:	
1) Route Optimization	2) Fuel change
Total Distance of Optimized Route 1 to 11 = 128 Km Fuel used in vehicle - Diesel	Total Distance of Optimized Route-1 to 11 = 128 Km Fuel used in vehicle -Natural Gas
Emission of CO ₂ $0.301*128*60,000 = 2,311,1680$ Kg CO ₂	Emission of CO ₂ = $0.331*128*60,000 = 2,542,080$ Kg CO ₂
Emission of NO _x = $0.001919* 128*60,000 = 14,737.92$ Kg Nox	Emission of NO _x = $0.000317* 128*60,000=2,434.56$ Kg NO _x
Emission of Black Carbon = $0.000241*128*60,000 = 1850.88$ Kg Black Carbon	Emission of Black Carbon = $0.0000002*128*60,000 = 0.1536$ Kg Black Carbon
Emission of PM _{2.5} from optimized route = $0.000146* 128*60,000 = 1121.28$ Kg PM _{2.5}	Emission of PM _{2.5} = $0.0000112*128*60,000 = 86.016$ Kg PM _{2.5}

CONCLUSION

From the present study, estimation of air pollutants emitted from municipal solid waste management strategies through modeling approach following conclusions can be drawn:

1. For BAU (Existing) scenario: In this scenario, 30% waste handle through Composting, 45% by Recycling and 25% Disposed at Landfill site. This Scenario emits overall emission 8,97,639MTCO_{2e} in 2021 which will reduce up to 7,70,985 in 2031.
2. Scenario-1 Increase Composting: In this scenario, 40% waste treated by Composting,45% by Recycling and 15% disposed at landfill site. This Scenario emits overall emission 8,97,693 MTCO_{2e} in 2021 which will reduce in 2030 up to 5,34,195 MTCO_{2e}.
3. Scenario-2 Increase Recycling: In this Scenario percentage of waste recycling was increase and 60% waste treated via recycling, 30% via Composting and 10% disposed at landfill site. This Scenario emits overall emission 8,97,693 MTCO_{2e} in 2021 which will reduce in 2030 up to 5,17,869 MTCO_{2e}.
4. Scenario-3 Fuel change: In this scenario waste was handle as per BAU but vehicle used for collection of MSW based on diesel were 50% changed with Natural Gas. This Scenario emits overall emission 8,97,693 MTCO_{2e} in 2021 which will reduce emission up to 6,12,201 MTCO_{2e} in 2030.
5. Scenario-4 Increase Composting & Recycling with Fuel change: In this scenario, 40% waste treated by Composting,50% by Recycling and 10% disposed at landfill site. With this vehicle used for collection of MSW based on diesel were 50% changed with Natural Gas. This Scenario emits overall emission 8,97,693 MTCO_{2e} in 2021 which will reduce in 2030 up to 5,34,195 MTCO_{2e}.
6. Route optimization was also carried out as an alternate scenario for reduction of air emission from collection-transportation sector. This scenario further divided into two

parts. In first part, distance travelled by vehicle was reduced from 144.27 km to 128km. This Scenario generates CO₂ emission from existing route of Ghatlodia ward is 2,605,516.2 Kg CO₂ which will reduce up to 2,311,1680 Kg CO₂ per Kg by optimizing route and second part was route optimization along with fuel change which reduces emission up to 2,542,080 Kg CO₂.

7. Based on results of reduction in air emission from all scenario, present study concludes that scenario-4 Increase Composting& Recycling along with Fuel change will be best option for handling of waste and reduction of air emission. As it reduces the percentage of waste goes for landfilling and recover more waste via increasing recycling and Composting. It also reduces the emission of NO_x, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀ and Black Carbon through fuel change.

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